

NEW ASPECTS OF NITROGEN FIXATION AND CONSERVATION IN THE SOIL. PART III INFLUENCE OF LIGHT ON BACTERIAL NUMBERS AND NITROGEN FIXATION.

BY N. R. DHAR AND E. V. SESHACHARYULU.

Nitrogen fixation is always greater in the soils exposed to sunlight than in those kept in dark or covered, while the numbers of azotobacter, total bacteria and fungi are less in the former than in the latter.

The optimum temperature for azotobacter is 35° in tropical soils as against 25° (26-30°) in temperate climates. The observed greater nitrogen fixation in the exposed soils is not at all due to the increase of temperature but is caused by sunlight.

On the addition of cellulosic substances, the available nitrogen decreases. Organic manures like cowdung, hay, molasses etc. are beneficial because they fix atmospheric nitrogen in the soil.

The process of fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in the soil has been believed to be entirely bacterial. Dhar and Mukherji (*Proc. Acad. Sci. U. P.*, 1934, 4, 175) have shown that the fixation of the nitrogen not only takes place in the ordinary soils but also in sterilised soils on the addition of sugars and exposed to sunlight. The authors concluded that nitrogen fixation in tropical soils is not only a bacterial process but is also due to photochemical and induced oxidations going on side by side, since the soil contains oxides of metals like iron, manganese, titanium etc. and is exposed to sunlight for several hours daily.

Further work was felt necessary to decide whether the fixation of nitrogen in the soil is mainly a bacterial process or due also to light and chemical agencies. The present paper deals with the following topics :

1. The nitrogen fixation on the addition of energy-rich substances to the soil.
2. The changes in the numbers of azotobacter, total bacteria, and fungi on the addition of energy-rich substances to the soil.
3. The influence of sunlight on nitrogen fixation, azotobacter, total bacteria and fungi in the soil.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The total nitrogen and carbon were estimated according to the method of Robinson, McLean and Williams (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1929, 19, 315). The soil

(50 g.) was treated with potassium chloride and magnesium oxide and absorbing the liberated ammonia in dilute sulphuric acid and the ammoniacal nitrogen was determined from the colorimetric estimation of the aminonium sulphate by a Duboscq colorimeter. For nitrate determination Devarda's alloy was used for the reduction of the nitrogen to ammonia.

Methods for Determining the Bacterial Numbers in the Soil.

General procedure.—The soil (0.1 g.) was carefully weighed in a sterile boiling test tube, 10 c.c. of autoclaved tap-water added, the tube shaken well for 5 minutes and then allowed to stand for half a minute. A series of sterile dilution tubes with 9 c.c. of autoclaved tap-water were taken and 1 c.c. of supernatant liquid from the original tube was transferred by a sterile 1 c.c. pipette with proper precautions to the first dilution tube and the mixture well shaken. Further dilutions were carried out in the same way upto a limit which was found out by experience until 1 c.c. of the mixture in the last dilution tube, when plated, allowed a growth of 40 to 300 colonies of bacteria. Platings were done by transferring 1 c.c. from the final and intermediate dilution tubes to sterile petri dishes and pouring 8 to 10 c.c. of the melted media and shaking the petri dishes in the usual way until the media were set to ensure an even distribution of the colonies.

Azotobacter.—Beijerinck's medium sterilised at 14 lbs. pressure for about 15 to 20 minutes was used.

The azotobacter plates were incubated at 30-31° for three days and counted. An average of 5 plates was taken. The types of colonies included in the count were greyish round colonies, round raised concentric, etc.

The total bacteria were determined using Thornton's media with mannitol as energy material and sterilised and counted as above with the difference that the incubation was for 7 days. Here total bacteria include actinomyces and not fungi.

Fungi.—The following medium was used :

Glucose	10 g.
Peptone	5.0
KH ₂ PO ₄	1.0
MgSO ₄ , 7H ₂ O	0.5
Distilled water	1000 c.c.

The ingredients were dissolved by boiling and enough normal sulphuric acid added to bring the reaction to p_{H} 3.6-3.8. Agar (25 g. approx.) was

added and dissolved by boiling ; the medium filtered and the final reaction adjusted to p_H 4.8 and sterilised as before.

Sterile containers were used as above without exposing them to air contamination and the usual procedure was followed. The moisture content of the soils was also simultaneously determined.

Nitrogen Fixation, Azotobacter and total Bacterial counts on the Application of Carbohydrates and Molasses to the Soil in Basins and Fields.

Garden soil (1 kg.) was mixed thoroughly with 20 g. of each of several energy-rich materials and 250 c.c. of water separately in enamelled basins (diameter 26 cm.) and exposed to sunlight for 8 hours daily. Some basins with the same substance were kept in a dark room in order to exclude light. In one set of the experiments with canesugar and glucose 2 g. of calcium carbonate were added. Water (160 c.c.) was added daily to the exposed basins and after every three days to the basins kept in the dark to maintain a uniform moisture content. During summer months 160 c.c. of water were added twice a day to the exposed basins and after every two days to the basins kept in the dark.

In the case of starch and glycerol the experiments were carried out with 5% of these substances. Before commencement of the experiments, estimations of nitrogen, total carbon and azotobacter numbers of the original soils were carried out. At regular intervals the nitrogen content, total carbon and azotobacter numbers of the exposed and dark soils were determined simultaneously. The mean temperature of the soils kept in sunlight and in dark was also recorded. The results are given below.

TABLE I.

Soil (1 kg.) + glucose (20 g. .

A. Exposed to sunlight.

Date.	NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Moisture.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.
Original soil						
4-2-36	0.0012%	0.0031%	0.0433%	0.4677%	1.3%	11.2
22-2-36	0.0016	0.0031	0.0433	1.1778	2.1	9.9
7-3-36	0.0028	0.0031	0.0456	1.0014	2.0	17.4
31-3-36	0.0032	0.0032	0.0477	0.8420	1.8	16.3
7-4-36	0.0045	0.0032	0.0500	0.6940	2.1	16.8
21-4-36	0.0038	0.0035	0.0500	0.6420	2.1	16.1
7-5-36	0.0034	0.0038	0.0488	0.5910	2.3	16.2
21-5-36	0.0033	0.0038	0.0488	0.5260	2.1	16.1
7-6-36	0.0030	0.0030	0.0488	0.5180	2.2	16.5

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 12.5 mg.

TABLE I (contd.).

B. Dark.

Date.	NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Moiture.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.
Original soil						
4-2-36	0.0012%	0.0031%	0.0433%	0.4677%	1.3%	11.2
22-2-36	0.0014	0.0031	0.0433	0.2016	3.0	18.0
7-3-36	0.0016	0.0031	0.0433	1.1224	3.1	37.8
21-3-36	0.0021	0.0031	0.0456	1.0210	3.2	170.0
7-4-36	0.0025	0.0031	0.0466	0.9088	3.6	228.0
21-4-36	0.0028	0.0031	0.0466	0.8078	3.6	320.0
7-5-36	0.0032	0.0032	0.0472	0.6662	3.2	395.0
21-5-36	0.0030	0.0032	0.0472	0.6088	3.3	350.0
7-6-36	0.0029	0.0032	0.0466	0.5546	3.2	345.0

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 6.5 mg.

TABLE II.

Soil (1 kg.) + starch (50 g.).

A. Exposed (Temp. 34—48°).

Date.	NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Moisture.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.
Original soil.						
10-3-36	0.0010%	0.0024%	0.0420%	0.4410%	1.6%	7.2
9-4-36	0.0010	0.0024	0.0420	—	2.0	6.8
30-4-36	0.0018	0.0024	0.0433	2.4425	1.9	8.2
20-5-36	0.0023	0.0025	0.0442	2.3700	2.0	9.1
20-6-36	0.0029	0.0025	0.0451	2.2765	2.2	15.6
16-7-36	0.0033	0.0025	0.0461	2.1753	2.5	19.8
28-7-36	0.0037	0.0025	0.0472	2.0932	2.7	28.2
7-10-36	0.0052	0.0026	0.0510	1.4411	3.0	38.6
7-11-36	0.0056	0.0026	0.0530	1.2592	2.8	31.2
7-12-36	0.0058	0.0026	0.0538	1.0181	3.2	39.4
2-1-37	0.0060	0.0026	0.0555	0.7217	3.4	32.8
6-2-37	0.0046	0.0026	0.0560	0.5953	3.5	28.5
2-3-37	0.0040	0.0028	0.0547	0.5684	3.0	16.5
11-4-37	0.0035	0.0033	0.0530	0.5486	3.0	9.5

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 7.58 mg.

TABLE II (contd.).

B. Dark (Temp. 28—38°).

Date.	NH ₃ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Moisture.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.
Original soil.						
10-3-36	0.0010%	0.0024%	0.0420%	0.4410%	1.6%	1.2
9-4-36	0.0010	0.0024	0.0420	—	3.2	8.1
30-4-36	0.0014	0.0024	0.0420	2.5182	3.0	11.2
20-5-36	0.0015	0.0024	0.0420	2.4761	3.5	18.5
20-6-36	0.0018	0.0024	0.0433	2.4137	3.8	26.8
16-7-36	0.0021	0.0024	0.0437	2.3352	4.0	46.0
28-7-36	0.0023	0.0024	0.0442	2.2654	4.2	98.6
7-10-36	0.0031	0.0025	0.0461	1.8286	4.8	205.5
7-11-36	0.0032	0.0025	0.0461	1.7614	4.1	265.5
7-12-36	0.0032	0.0024	0.0466	1.5382	4.6	305.6
2-1-37	0.0035	0.0024	0.0472	1.3124	4.5	365.5
6-2-37	0.0032	0.0025	0.0477	1.0538	3.5	380.0
2-3-37	0.0030	0.0025	0.0482	0.7854	4.0	385.0
11-4-37	0.0024	0.0026	0.0482	0.5368	4.0	300.0

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 3.13 mg.

The experimental results show (Table II) that the nitrogen content (both ammoniacal and total nitrogen) and azotobacter numbers increase on the application of carbohydrates to the soils. Exactly similar results have been obtained with other carbohydrates and glycerol. According to the bacterial theory the nitrogen fixation should be parallel to the azotobacter numbers.

But the above results show quite the reverse. The azotobacter numbers in the soils kept in the dark are approximately ten times greater than in the soils exposed to sunlight but the nitrogen fixation is almost double in the exposed soils than in those kept in dark. Moreover, the oxidation of the energy-rich materials is much quicker in the exposed soils than in those kept in dark. Further, the size of the azotobacter colonies developed on the plates containing the soils kept in the dark is much bigger

than those obtained from the exposed ones. A tentative suggestion may be offered as to the reason of the differences in size that the generation time of the azotobacter in the soils kept in the dark is less compared to those in the exposed one probably to sunlight inhibiting the growth. It can be concluded that along with the bacterial fixation of nitrogen in tropical soils, there is considerable fixation due to the photochemical oxidation of the energy-rich substances and that is why although the number of azotobacter in the soils exposed to sunlight is much less than in those kept in the dark the fixation of nitrogen is much higher in sunlight. It also appears that the fixation is not much affected by the addition of calcium carbonate. This behaviour is possibly due to the fact that the soils with which we carried on experiments are rich in calcium. In the case of starch, sugars are detected by Benedict's solution both in the exposed soils as well as in those kept in the dark. Control experiments with blank soil in basins both in light and in darkness were done but no fixation of nitrogen was observed.

Field Experiments.

TABLE III.

Substance.	N fixed per g. of C oxidised.		Substance.	N fixed per g. of C oxidised.	
	Sunlight.	Dark.		Sunlight.	Dark.
Canesugar (2%) + CaCO ₃	15.8 mg.	10.5 mg.	Mannitol (2%)	12.8 mg.	6.9 mg.
Canesugar (2%)	14.6	10.2	Dextrin (2%)	13.03	5.98
Glucose (2%) + CaCO ₃	12.5	6.5	Fructose (2%)	11.9	6.8
Glycerol (5%)	6.04	2.76	Maltose (2%)	12.6	6.8
Starch (5%)	7.58	3.13	Galactose (2%)	12.09	6.7

The size of the plots chosen was 4' × 4'. The energy-rich materials were added to the fields (amounts being recorded at the top of each table) with water and thoroughly mixed. The experiments were all carried out under aerobic conditions. Comparative experiments were also carried out by exposing one set of plots to sunlight and another corresponding set with the same amount of substance being covered with wooden planks leaving enough space for aeration but excluding sunlight. The exposed plots were watered after every four days and the covered ones every seven days to maintain a uniform moisture content. Both the covered and the exposed plots were dug up every eight days simultaneously. At regular intervals the nitrogen content, total

carbon, azotobacter and total bacterial numbers were determined. The temperature of the exposed plots during the months of April, May and June varied from 61° to 38° at depths varying from 0 to 6" and that of the covered plots from 41° to 31.5° at the same depths. Control plots were kept, both exposed and covered. In these field experiments after the addition of the energy-rich substances, the soil was immediately taken and the total nitrogen and total carbon were determined.

The mean values of these estimations show that in a plot of area 4' × 4' containing 5 kg. of added glucose and exposed to sunlight the nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised amounted to 14.0 mg., while in a similar plot, kept covered, the amount of nitrogen fixed per gram of carbon oxidised was 7.26 mg. The effect of adding 4 kg. of starch in a plot of the same area yielded values of nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised to the extent of 16.5 mg. when exposed to sunlight and 5.9 mg. when kept covered.

These figures show that nitrogen fixation takes place and also azotobacter and total bacterial numbers increase and that the fixation of nitrogen in the exposed plots is always much greater than in the corresponding covered plots, although the azotobacter and total bacterial numbers are less in the former than in the latter. There is no correlation between the nitrogen fixation and azotobacter numbers (*cf.* Waksman, "Principles of Soil Microbiology", 1931, p. 113). The results obtained fully substantiate the conclusion that in tropical soils along with bacterial fixation, photochemical fixation of atmospheric nitrogen is prominent.

Table IV shows the amounts of nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised both in light and dark or covered.

TABLE IV.

Field trials in a plot 4' × 4' containing the carbohydrate.

	Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised.	
	Exposed to sunlight.	Dark.
Glucose (5 kg.)	14.0 mg.	7.26 mg.
Molasses (10 kg.)	8.9	3.56
Starch (4 kg.)	16.5	5.9

The above results show conclusively that for the same amount of carbon oxidised the nitrogen fixation in light is much greater than that in the dark. According to Dhar and Mukerji (*Proc. Acad. Sci. U.P.*, 1935, 5, 61)

the formation of nitric oxide may be the first step in the fixation of nitrogen. The formation of nitric oxide according to the equation

is endothermal. A gram molecular weight of these energy materials on oxidation liberates energy much in excess of that required for the combination of nitrogen and oxygen forming nitric oxide. It seems that nitrogen fixation is considerably aided not only by the energy obtained from the oxidation of the carbohydrates but also by the absorption of the incident light.

In the case of starch and glycerol (5%) and molasses (10 kg. in fields) the nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon is small when compared with others because of the high concentrations of the energy materials applied to the soil.

Influence of Temperature and Sunlight on Nitrogen Fixation and Azotobacter Count on the Application of Glucose to the Soil in Basins.

It has been stated (*Nature*, 1937, 139, 894) that the photochemical view of nitrogen fixation has to be tested by carrying on experiments in dark under exactly the same temperature conditions as in sunlight. The following experiments were carried out to examine this aspect.

The garden soil (200 g.) was mixed with pure glucose (4 g.) and moisture content made up to 16% in small enamelled basins (diameter 16 cm.) and incubated at temperatures varying from 11° to 60°. For comparison one basin containing the similarly treated soil with glucose was exposed to sunlight. The results are given below.

TABLE V.

Soil (200 g.) + glucose (4 g.).

A. Exposed to sunlight (mean temp. 42°).				B. Dark (temp 10-12°).		
Date.	Total N.	Total C.	*Azotobacter	Total N.	Total C.	*Azotobacter.
Original soil						
26-2-37	0.0323%	0.3180%	2.05	0.0323	0.3180	2.05
27-2-37	0.0323	1.1168	—	0.0323	1.1156	—
23-3-37	0.0344	0.9512	13.0	0.0323	1.0472	4.0
16-4-37	0.0375	0.7026	20.5	0.0323	0.9186	6.0
13-5-37	0.0411	0.4468	22.5	0.0323	0.7462	4.5
31-5-37	0.0407	0.4356	16.0	0.0323	0.5938	3.5
20-6-37	0.0400	0.4214	14.0	0.0318	0.4684	3.0
10-7-37	0.0396	0.4158	8.5	0.0318	0.3987	2.5

Nitrogen fixed per g. of C oxidised = 13.1 mg. Nitrogen fixed per g. of C. oxidised = nil.

* Expressed as per g. of dry soil in millions.

TABLE VI.

Soil (200 g.) + glucose (4 g.)

Dark (Temp. 35°).

Date.	Total N.	Total C.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.
26-2-37	0.0323	0.3180	2.05
27-2-37	0.0323	1.1168	—
23-3-37	0.0338	0.9816	28.0
16-4-37	0.0353	0.7682	110.0
13-5-37	0.0368	0.5618	180.0
31-5-37	0.0375	0.4468	200.0
20-6-37	0.0371	0.4238	160.0
10-7-37	0.0368	0.4199	86.0

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 7.76 mg.

Results of several such experiments at different temperatures together with the nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised at these temperatures have been recorded below in Table VII.

TABLE VII.

Summary of results obtained at different temperatures.

Temp.	Maximum number of azotobacter.*	N fixed.	Temp.	Maximum number of azotobacter.*	N fixed.
42° (Exposed)	22.5	13.1 mg.	40° (Dark)	98.0	3.97 mg.
10-12° (Dark)	6.0	Nil.	45° „	78.0	3.03
25° „	126.0	4.8	50° „	7.5	1.6
30° „	175.0	6.4	60° „	Nil	Nil
35° „	200.0	7.76			

From the foregoing results it is clear that the optimum temperature for nitrogen fixation in the dark is 35° as against about 28° (26°-30°) observed in temperate countries. At 11° and 60° the fixation is nil. The nitrogen fixed in the exposed soil, the temperature of which varied from 40° to 44°, is much greater than that in the incubated soils kept in the dark. The result definitely proves that the increase of temperature in sunlight is not at all the factor responsible for the greater nitrogen fixation observed, which is mainly due to the utilisation of solar energy for nitrogen fixation.

* Expressed as per g. of dry soil in millions.

Another important point that we have observed from the experimental results in basins and fields is that the available nitrogen (the sum of ammoniacal and nitric nitrogen) also increases on the addition of carbohydrates and molasses to the soil. The experience of the other workers in temperate countries is quite different.

In the control plots no increase in the available total nitrogen nor in the bacterial counts is observed.

Nitrogen Fixation, Azotobacter, Total Bacteria and Fungi Counts on the application of Cellulosic substances like Filter paper Cowdung and Hay to the soil in Basins and Fields.

Since doubt has been expressed about the activity of nitrogen fixing organisms in presence of cellulose, the changes in the azotobacter and the total bacterial numbers on the addition of cellulose to the soil were also investigated. Since fungi also take an active part, the change in their numbers was also studied. The following cellulosic substances, *e.g.*, (i) filter paper, (ii) cowdung, (iii) hay were used. Experiments were carried out with cowdung plus hay and hay plus molasses in fields. Analysis of hay and filter paper is shown below

	Hay.	Filter paper.
Total N	0.7778%	
Total C	41.674%	41.56%

The results are given below.

TABLE VII.

Soil (1 kg.) + filter paper (20 g.)

Date.	NH ₃ -N.	A. Exposed.			Mois- ture.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.
		NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.		
Original soil						
30-10-36	0.0011%	0.0020%	0.0540%	0.567%	2.2%	2.4
22-12-36	0.0008	0.0018	0.0540	—	3.8	3.7
20-1-37	0.0007	0.0016	0.0560	—	3.1	7.7
20-3-37	0.0006	0.0014	0.0583	—	3.0	12.5
7-5-37	0.0006	0.0012	0.0646	—	3.5	20.5
7-6-37	0.0006	0.0011	0.0677	—	3.1	27.2
8-7-37	0.0007	0.0014	0.0666	0.7012	—	18.0
13-9-37	0.0014	0.0021	0.0646	0.6704	—	12.0

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 18.1 mg. (scale).

TABLE VIII (contd.).

Soil (1 kg.) + filter paper (20 g.).

Date.	NH ₃ -N.	B. Dark. NO ₃ -N.	Total N.	Total C.	Mois- ture.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.
Original soil						
30-10-36	0.0011%	0.0020%	0.0540%	0.5670	2.2%	2.4
22-12-36	0.0007	0.0015	0.0540	—	4.8	4.3
20-1-37	0.0006	0.0012	0.0540	—	4.2	5.7
20-3-37	0.0006	0.0010	0.0552	—	4.0	25.5
7-5-37	0.0006	0.0009	0.0567	—	3.0	65.0
7-6-37	0.0006	0.0009	0.0575	—	—	80.0
8-7-37	0.0006	0.0009	0.0583	—	—	92.5
13-9-37	0.0008	0.0001	0.0608	0.6486	—	145.0

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 9.2 mg. (calc.).

Identical experiments with 50 g. of cowdung in 1 kg. of soil showed the amount of nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised to be 20.5 mg. when kept in sunlight as against 6.5 mg. in dark. Similar experiments repeated on a field scale in a plot 4 ft. by 4 ft. gave figures as in tables below.

TABLE IX.

Plot 4 ft. by 4 ft. containing 20 kg. of cowdung.

Date.	Total N	Total C.	A. Exposed.			
			Moisture.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.	Total bacteria. per g. of dry soil in millions.	Fungi per g. of dry soil.
Original soil						
10-2-37	0.0323%	0.3294%	1.7%	1.05	10.7	22000
12-2-37	0.0356	0.7126	—	—	—	—
7-3-37	0.0368	0.6354	3.0	6.5	20.5	32000
5-4-37	0.0388	0.5616	3.5	15.8	65.5	41000
29-4-37	0.0424	0.4826	3.0	32.0	160.0	30000
25-5-37	0.0442	0.4108	3.0	30.0	170.0	28000
12-6-37	0.0466	0.3825	3.5	28.5	168.5	28000
28-9-37	0.0446	0.3789	3.2	15.8	115.2	25000

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 33.3 mg.

TABLE IX (contd.).

Plot 4 ft. by 4 ft. containing 20 kg. of cowdung.

B. Covered.

	Total N.	Total C.	Moisture	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions	Total bac- teria per g. of dry soil in millions.	Fungi per g. of dry soil.
Original soil						
10-2-37	0.0356%	0.3987%	1.8%	1.15	11.2	23000
12-2-37	0.0381	0.7218	—	—	—	—
7-3-37	0.0385	0.6586	4.0	7.5	26.5	40000
5-4-37	0.0392	0.5944	4.0	21.5	112.0	56000
20-4-37	0.0403	0.5168	3.5	48.5	270.0	89000
25-5-37	0.0411	0.4684	4.0	85.0	315.0	48000
12-6-37	0.0420	0.4158	4.5	65.5	335.0	46000
28-9-37	0.0428	0.4012	5.0	49.5	300.0	41000

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 14.6 mg.

TABLE X.

Plot 4 ft. by 4 ft. containing 5 kg. of hay.

A. Exposed.

Date.	Total N.	Total C.	Moisture	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.	Total bac- teria per g of dry soil in millions	Fungi per gram of dry soil
Original soil						
22-1-37	0.0323%	0.3488%	1.7%	1.5	12.7	27600
3-3-37	0.0350	—	3.0	10.5	25.0	38000
7-4-37	0.0381	—	3.5	20.5	85.6	36000
5-5-37	0.0417	—	3.0	43.5	177.5	33000
29-5-37	0.0442	—	3.5	55.5	220.0	30000
15-6-37	0.0466	—	3.0	45.0	190.0	28000
23-9-37	0.0512	0.6724	4.0	38.5	225.0	29000
28-10-37	0.0500	0.5736	4.5	21.5	195.5	26000

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 54 mg.

B. Covered.

Date.	Total N.	Total C.	Moisture	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions.	Total bac- teria per g of dry soil in millions	Fungi per gram of dry soil
Original soil						
22-1-37	0.0442	0.4199	1.8	1.14	13.3	25100
3-3-37	0.0456	—	4.0	18.0	32.0	43000
7-4-37	0.0472	—	4.5	35.5	140.5	48000
5-5-37	0.0491	—	4.0	55.6	231.0	44000
29-5-37	0.0512	—	4.0	70.0	300.0	46000
15-6-37	0.0525	—	—	82.0	360.0	40000
23-9-37	0.0560	0.7854	5.2	92.8	385.0	41000
28-10-37	0.0560	0.0459	4.8	75.3	315.6	36000

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 14 mg.

TABLE XI.

Substance.	Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised. (Basin experiment).	
	Exposed.	Dark.
Cowdung (5%)	20.53 mg.	6.55 mg.
Filter paper (2%)	18.1	9.2
	(Field trials)	
Cowdung (10 kg.)	36.58 mg.	16.6 mg.
Cowdung (20 ,,)	33.33	14.64
Hay (5 ,,)	54.0	14.0

Greater nitrogen fixation is observed with hay plus molasses and hay plus cowdung than with hay alone. Not much of increase in the numbers of fungi is observed since our soils are not acidic but slightly alkaline (p_H 7.8). The fixation of nitrogen is again much greater and almost double or treble in the exposed soils than in those kept in dark, or covered.

In tropical countries almost a constant yield of crop is possible due to the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen by the oxidation of the energy materials contained in the plant residues left in the soil.

The available nitrogen in the soil decreases in the beginning unlike in the case of carbohydrates, on the addition of cellulosic substances. No increase of total nitrogen and bacterial counts is observed in the control plots without the addition of energy materials.

*Nitrogen Fixation, Azotobacter, Total Bacteria and Fungi Counts on
the Application of Bulter and Ghee (clarified butter)
to the Soil.*

According to Rubner (*Arch. Hyg.*, 1922, 91, 290) only 22.9 % of butter fats added to soil (4.5 g. of fat to 200 g. of soil) were decomposed during a period of one year, and 31.8 % in 12 years; other fats were decomposed at different rates (Waksman, "Principles of Soil Microbiology" 1931, p. 404). The investigation was undertaken to find out whether fats are decomposed in the soil under tropical conditions and any nitrogen fixation takes place as a result of their oxidation. For this purpose butter and ghee (clarified butter) were taken. Since azotobacter is the effective nitrogen-fixing bacteria and a number of aerobic bacteria and fungi take an active part in the decomposition of fats, the changes in the numbers of azotobacter, total bacteria and fungi were carefully investigated. Finally the influence of sunlight on the bacterial counts and nitrogen fixation on the addition of butter and ghee was also studied. The experiments were carried out as in other cases both in basins and in field conditions.

TABLE XII.

Plot 4' x 4' containing 2 kg. of ghee.

	A. Exposed.					
	Total N.	Total C.	Moisture.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions	Total bacteria per g. of dry soil in millions.	Fungi per g. of soil
Control (mean)	0.3813%	0.40792%	3.29%	1.454	13.11	23922

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 11.7 mg..

	B. Dark					
	Total N.	Total C.	Moisture.	Azotobacter per g. of dry soil in millions	Total bacteria per g. of dry soil in millions.	Fungi per g. of soil
Control (mean)	0.0482	0.5213	3.68	1.26	13.93	2433.3

Nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised = 4.6 mg.

Experiments with butter gave similar results.

The foregoing results show clearly that butter and ghee decompose slowly and definite fixation of atmospheric nitrogen takes place as a result of the energy liberated by their oxidation in the soil. It is also evident that when compared to carbohydrates, the oxidation of fats in the soil is a much slower process. The azotobacter and total bacteria increase in number on the addition of butter and ghee to the soil. In this case also the fixation of nitrogen is much greater in the exposed soils than in those kept in dark or covered, whereas the bacterial and fungi numbers are less in the former than in the latter. This clearly indicates that the action of light in the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen when any energy material is added to the soil is a general phenomenon. The available nitrogen, however, decreased in the soil on the application of butter and ghee. In our field experiments, the number of azotobacter in the dark went up to 645 millions per gram of soil on the addition of molasses from 12 millions present in the original un-molassed soil with cellulosic and fatty materials, the increase in the azotobacter numbers in the dark is much less than with carbohydrates, *e.g.*, 93 millions per g. of soil with hay and 94 millions per g. of soil with ghee (clarified butter). In presence of sunlight, however, the increase in azotobacter numbers on the addition of energy materials to soil is always much less than in the dark.